

BALLAL DHIPI IN NADIA DISTRICT OF WEST BENGAL: AN ARCHAEOLOGICAL OVERVIEW

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Abstract

Ballal Dhupi(mound) is a historical as well as an archaeological site of 13,000 sq.m area, located at Bamanpukur Bazar on way to Mayapur at a distance of about 25 k.m from Krishnanagar which is believed to be the part of Raja *Ballal Sena's* kingdom, who was the third ruler of the *Sena* dynasty in Bengal, in 12th century. At about 1979 AD a preliminary survey was conducted by the Archaeology Department of Calcutta University, under the supervision of Dr. Ashok Datta. Later on, in 1980 the site was taken over by the Archaeological Survey of India, Kolkata circle. After a series of extensive survey of the site and analysis of the findings the experts concluded that the site was a *Stupa* (Buddhist religious edifice) having certain features of temple complex of 8th /9th century, and was perhaps a seat of learning and pilgrimage up to the 11th century. The site is now protected by the ASI and enlisted as the *Monuments of National Importance*.

Key Words: Heritage, Stupa, Style & motifs

Introduction

Remnants of cultural heritage of ancient Bengal may exhibit its huge affinity in throughout West Bengal. The present study is to highlight the Ballal Sena's Dhupi (Ballal Sena's mound), which reposes strong connection with the Great *Ballal Sena* (1158-1179 C.E.), the fourth independent ruler of *Sena* dynasty (1070-1230 C.E.) of ancient Bengal. The study was done on a fortified monument which is located in Bamanpukur area (on way to Mayapur, at a distance of 25 KM. from the Krishnanagar railway station) in Nadia district of West Bengal. The complex has occupied about a 13,000 sq.mt. area surrounding a mound having a height of 9 m. After Raja *Ballal Sena*, local people call the entire complex as '*Ballal Sen's Dhupi*'.

In 1979, primary exploration activities were conducted and some test pits were dug by the post graduate students of Department of Archaeology of University of Calcutta, which was led by Late Dr. Ashok Datta of the said academic department. Later on, in 1980 ASI took over the charge of the complex and a number of excavations were carried out successively from 1982 to 1989. (IAR, 1982-83; 1983-84; 1984-85; 1985-86; 1986-87; 1987-88; 1988-89). Later on, ASI partitioned the site into two parts – the mound and the fortified remains of the fort. For now, both the parts are protected by ASI and enlisted as the *Monuments of National Importance*.

Fig.1 An overview of the site from the north-east boundary

Historical background

During the mid of 11th Century Bengal experienced a distinguished political mess after the fall of *Pala Empire* (900-1050 C.E.). Many *Samanta Rajas* (territorial vassals) who were subordinates to the *Pala Empire* claimed themselves as the individual rulers of their territory. It is believed that, one of them named *Samanta Sena* and his son *Hemanta Sena* took the opportunity to reunite the mutineers. In 1080 CE. the *Sena* dynasty was established under the reign of *Hemanta Sena* (1080-1096 CE). He became the first Raja of *Sena* Empire with the honorary epithet of the *Mahārājādhirāja* (King of kings) and the *Rājarakshāsudaksha* (competent savior of the kings) of the *Rarh* Bengal (lies between the Chotanagpur plateau in the west and the Ganges delta in the east) (Jarret & Sarkar, 1949; Vasu, 1987; Rahman, 2018).

Somehow, the *Samanta Sena* had a genealogical connection with a remote ancestor of *Sena* dynasty named *Bir Sena* or *Vira Sena* (Jarret, Sarkar, 1949; Rahman, 2018) who belonged to the *Chandravanshi* (Lunar dynasty) *Brahma-Kshatriya* (Brahmins turned to warrior clans) clan of *Karnat* (Karnataka, South India) (Jour. of Asi. Soc. ,1838; Majumdar, 1945; Vasu, 1987).

On the contrary, the rulers of *Suket* and *Mandi* estate of Punjab claimed themselves to be the ancestors of the *Sena*'s of Bengal. They believed that they belonged to the '*Atri gotra*' of the *Chandravanshi* line of Rajputs and consequently claimed as descendants of the *Pandava* family of *Mahabharata*. The progenitors of this line are believed to have ruled for 1700 years in *Indraprastha* (now in Delhi), until one *Khemraj*, the last ruler of the early dynasty was dispelled by his *Wazir* (vizier) *Bisarp*, who then controlled the throne. (Punj. Gaze. 1920; Beotra, 1927; Vasu, 1987)

*Khemraj*losinghis kingdom of *Indraprastha*, fled awayeastward and settled in Bengal, where thirteen of his successors were said to have ruled for 350 years. Their capital was at *Lakshmanapuri* on the banks of the river Ganges. The most distinguished ruler of this dynasty was *Lakshmana Sena*, who was said to have extended his conquests to Kanauj, Nepal and Orissa and founded *Gaur city* in Malda district and renamed it as Lakshanauti or *Lakshmanabati* after himself. One of his successors *Ballal Sena* chose *Nuddia* (Nadia) as his capital near the confluence of the river Bhagirathi and Jalangi (Punj. Gaze. 1920; Beotra, 1927; Vasu, 1987).

A number of incised copperplates were discovered from various parts of Bengal in last two centuries. Notably among those were **a)** *Kesava Sena*'s (Ballal's grandson) plate from zilla Bakherganj pargana; **b)** Edilpur (now in Bangladesh) (Jour. of Asi. Soc., 1838); **c)** *VijaySena*'s (Ballal's father) plate from Barrackpore, district North 24 Parganas(1910); **d)** *BallalSena*'s plate from Naihati, district North 24 Parganas (1911); **e)** *Lakshman Sena*'s (Ballal's son) plates from Tarpandighi, district Dinajpur (1875);**f)** Dighirpar-Bakultala, Sundarban, South 24 Parganas (1886); **g)** Anulia, district Nadia (1898); **h)** Govindapur, South 24 Parganas (1919); **i)** Saktipur, district Murshidabad (1984) (Sen, 1942; Sanyal,2010), which are illustrious glorification of the royal line of *Sena* dynasty. The plates are mostly of grants of *Bardhan bhukti* and *Gram bhukti* to the Brahmins and for sacred and other religious purposes. The ten armed *Sadashiva* incised copperplate of *Ballal Sena* from Naihati (Jour. of Asi. Soc., 1838; Sen, 1942; Sanyal, 2010)and mention of having golden *Shiva* emblem on his throne in *Deo-para Prasasti*(Sen,1942) arealso noteworthy. Alongside, Tarpan dighi copperplate exhibits the grant of *avadhapa*, a rent-free plain land belonging to the deity of Buddhist monastery during the second reign of *Lakshmana Sena* (Sen, 1942; Sanyal, 2010).

Fig.2 Seal of Sadashiva on the BallalSena copper plate grant, from Naihati(Jour. of Asi. Soc., 1838).

On the support of the above, Abul Fazl Allami's (Grand *Wazir* of Emperor *Akbar* and author of *Akbar-nama*) *Ain-i-Akbari* (third volume of *Akbar-nama*) provides corresponding feedback. The descriptions and the genealogical evidences for the *Sena's* are given in *Ain-i-Akbari* often resembles with those found in copper plate inscriptions (Jour. of Asi. Soc., 1838; Jarret & Sarkar, 1949; Rahman, 2018).

Archaeological significance

Presently, the mound is covered an area of 128 x 100 m. The series of excavations have revealed a massive brick wall measuring 4.10 m. in width and 3.48 m. in height from the original ground level. From the study it can be assumed that the wall was repaired at least twice after its initial construction. The bricks from the initial phase measured 16 x 10 x 4 cm whereas in the later phases the bricks of different dimensions were introduced along with the bricks of the earlier construction. In the later phases of construction, bricks of 21 x 18 x 4 cm size became common. The defenses were manifested through a fortified wall of length of 22.70 m. on the eastern boundary of the mound and it is 50 m. long in the southern periphery. At a later stage during period of second phase renovation an outer wall of 1.68 m. thick was additionally constructed. The wall continues parallelly to the earlier wall at least on the southern side. The nature of the defenses points out that they were designed for safety and security of the settlement. In the midst of the settlement, remains of extensive brick-built flooring were observed.

Another brick structure measuring 8 m. of extant height has been observed in one of the trenches. The approach of the structure was relieved with offset projections at regular intervals. The diminishing dimensions producing a pyramidal elevation was another notable feature of this structure. The extensive ground plan was of cruciform pattern as has been observed from the exposed portion of the mound.

This form was retained in all of the stages of repair. In the top most level a brick edging was provided in an identical mode to the rammed lime-surkhi (terracotta brick dust) flooring. On the south-eastern corner a terracotta brick made fire-place was observed in circular form having 70 cm diameter at top and 50 cm at the bottom perhaps used as a *yagna kunda* (sacrificial fire place).

From the entire observations four phases of floorings have been encountered. The upper most was featured by a rammed lime-surkhi floor with brick edging. Remains of a brick flooring which appeared beneath were more extensive than the upper one; however its plan could not be fully understood. The next two consecutive floor levels were more elevated which might be for protection from inundation. Contextually, earlier the river Ganga was flowing close to the complex, which has now shifted about 4 km away.

Fig .3 Schematic diagram of the ground plan of the site (not to scale)

Style and motifs

It is observed that the exposed structure which represents a religious edifice was in all likelihood a temple of ‘*pancharatha*’ style, the width of which was 1.90 m, built of brick, the size of which varies but mostly it is 20×16×4 cm. The arms of the *ratha* projections which were designed with offsets were having a length of 5.50 m north-south and 3.15 m. east-west and the central projection being 14 m. long. This stupendous structure of 7 m. long from the foundation was laid on a brick platform which was also 1 m. high from the ground. The same is evidenced in the south-western corner. The medial space between the outer wall of the structure and the inner wall was 1.76 m. from surface. The inward structure was also in compatibility with its replication and similarly of ‘*pancharatha*’ style. The length of its projected arms was 5.50 m.in north-south direction and 3.15 m. in east-west respectively. The central projection was 9.40 m. of length. The nature of this massive structure, which through its exposed parts illustrates a cruciform plan inside a bigger cross, was ambiguous as the projected walls did not have a superstructure over them.

It was further to be noted that the use of the intermediate space between the inner and the outer parts of the structure which apparently served the purpose of circumambulation is not distinct. As yet no working plan has been found to prove its use. The structure underwent several

renovations and repairs in its upper level. At least two floor levels were observed. On the topmost level a brick edged pathway was built towards the last stage of assignment for circumambulation. In the upper part of the structure in its reconstructed portions as revealed in corners five-fold projections, slightly outward cornices were formed by molded bricks. The monotony of walls was broken by the provision of niches. It appeared that at a later phase the upper part of the structure was renovated as a shrine. There were traces of lime plaster of water channels used for disposing of the logged rain water. On the eastern side of inner structure, basalt made crocodile faced gargoyle, which is ended above a narrow circular well (*kunda*), is still in working condition.

Findings

On the lime-surkhi floor in a trench from the inner structure, a good number of copper objects were encountered. The objects included spouted lotas (small ritualistic water vessels), lamps, ladles and a number of cylindrical cases, the use of which in all probability was for preserving valuable records.

A good number of stucco figurines with human and demonic heads (*Gana*) and decorative motifs were recovered from the top level.

Fig.4 stucco figurines from the site (IAR.1985-87)

The discovered stucco figurines exhibit prominent human features. Most of the female head sare found with well combed hair with a prominent parting in between along with circular dots on their forehead, which may be the indication of applying vermilion or alike. Some of them are with topknot and bun.

Among the *ganas* elliptical depression is seen on the forehead, demonstrative of a third eye. Also, their round protruding eyes and grinning faces elucidate their demonic outlook. A complete stucco figure of a *gana* has been found. He is seated on his left leg with right leg on top, having a thread like form hanging from his left shoulder (perhaps *yagnapavita*; sacred thread) and continued to the waist region. Also, a good number of bangles are observed on the upper arms and on the wrists, and anklets in the ankle regions. A crown like appearance can be observed on its head though not so prominent.

A large number of architectural and pottery remains have been recovered from the same level. The ceramic artifacts comprised of hand is, jars, bowls, dishes in red ware are mostly unslipped and a few are slipped with dull grey material having impression of leaves, flowers and blocks of miniature squares on the outer surface.

Conclusion

It is very apparent that the present site was once a popular habitation for the people of the contemporary period. From the literature reviews and the findings, it is observed that the present site was once used as religious shrine though it does not specify the actual religious beliefs of the settlers. Taking into account of the context of using of ritualistic sacrificial fire (*yagna*) and presence of *ganas* it is observed that both appeared in the belief system of Hinduism as well as Buddhism. Similarly, the ritualistic utensils which have been unearthed were used in the religious practices of both the religions. Cylindrical cases may be used for the protection of the important documents perhaps manuscripts. The female figurines may demonstrate the *nartakees* (dancers) or perhaps the *devdasis* (women dedicated to the service of the deity-often temple dancers) existed during the period.

From the inscriptions of *Deopara-prasasti* and *Balla lSena's* copperplate from Naihati, it can be assumed that the *BallalSena* was *shaiva* by his beliefs. From the *Tarpandighi* copperplate inscription it is known that grant was given to the Buddhist monastery by *Lakshmana Sena* which may reflect the patronage view on Buddhism. However, comparing the identical features from the remains of *Vikramshila Vihare* experts consider this site as a religious complex of 8th century which might be transformed later into a seat of learning and pilgrimage till 11th century. Thus, further detailed study may enlighten with many hidden facts regarding the *Ballal Dhipi* of Nadia district as a part of cultural heritage of West Bengal and may contribute to the future research on Bengal heritage.

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